

TABLE 2—DATA OF THE THIOSEMICARBAZONES VI AND VII

Ar	R	% Yield	m.p. °C	MTC µg/ml
C ₆ H ₅ -	H	48.4	236	8
C ₆ H ₅ -	CH ₃	66.6	311	64
p-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	H	48.7	231	8
p-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	68.3	298	64
p-OH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	48.2	248	8
p-CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	78.2	265	64
p-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	48.1	238	8
p-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	76.9	275	64
p-Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	42.1	298(d)	16
p-Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	77.1	302	-
p-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	H	42.6	245	-
p-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	77.6	336	-
m-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	49.8	219-20	8
m-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	74.9	283	32
m-H ₃ C-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	48.0	230-31	8
m-H ₃ C-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	66.5	294	32
o-H ₃ C-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	50.7	238	8
o-H ₃ C-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	69.3	288	32

All the above compounds gave satisfactory C, N and S analyses.

is the minimum concentration which inhibits almost completely the growth of the test bacterium.

It is evident from the experimental data (Table 2) that *p*-(2,4-diarylamino-6-s-triazinyl-amino)-benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazones (VI) have higher tuberculostatic activity than the corresponding acetophenone thiosemicarbazone analogues (VII). The intermediate compounds II-V do not possess any significant activity against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* reflecting on the key role of thiosemicarbazone moiety in the antimycobacterial activity of the title compounds.

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Studies on Antitubercular Agents. Preparation of 2-Arylamino-4-(4-Carboethoxyanilino)-6-Isonicotinylhydrazino-1,3,5-Triazine

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LITERATURE reveals that a number of studies has been carried out on the chemotherapeutic potentialities of 1,3,5-triazine derivatives. It was thought that incorporation of substituted amino-1,3,5-triazine moiety into the tuberculostatic agent isonicotinic acid hydrazide, might modify the biological activities. Thus, 2,4,6-trichloro-1,3,5-triazine and ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate were reacted to produce 2-(4-carboethoxyanilino)-4,6-dichloro-1,3,5-triazine, which on reaction with isonicotinic acid hydrazide and subsequently with different aromatic amines gave 2-arylamino-4-(4-carboethoxyanilino)-6-isonicotinylhydrazino-1,3,5-triazine¹⁻⁴.

2-arylamino-4-(4-carboethoxyanilino)-6-isonicotinylhydrazino-1,3,5-triazine.

Experimental

Preparation of 2-(4-carbethoxyanilino)-4,6-dichloro-1,3,5-triazine : 2,4,6-Trichloro-1,3,5-triazine (0.01 mole) and ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate (0.01 mole) were separately dissolved in acetone (100 ml) and mixed at 0°. To it, NaOH (aqueous 4%; 100 ml) was added dropwise and mechanically stirred at 0-5°. The contents poured on ice, titrated with HCl (5 N), filtered and crystallised from THF, m.p. 284° (reported m.p. 282-87°). (Found : C, 50.40 ; Cl, 24.8 ; N, 19.25. C₁₂H₁₀Cl₂N₄O₂ requires C, 51.25 ; Cl, 25.27 ; N, 19.97%).

Preparation of 2-(4-carbethoxyanilino)-4-chloro-6-isonicotinylhydrazino-1,3,5-triazine : Isonicotinic acid hydrazide (INH, 0.08 mole) and 2-(4-carbethoxyanilino)-4,6-dichloro-1,3,5-triazine (0.08 mole) were dissolved in dioxane at 10 to 15°, followed by dropwise addition of NaHCO₃ (1 M; 90 ml) and stirring at 30-35° for 3 hr. The product isolated and crystallised from ethanol (95%), m.p. 325°. (Found : C, 56.22 ; H, 3.91 ; N, 24.38. C₁₈H₁₆ClN₇O₃ requires C, 55.89 ; H, 4.14 ; N, 25.36%).

Preparation of 2-arylamino-4-(4-carbethoxyanilino)-6-isonicotinylhydrazino-1,3,5-triazine : Amine (0.032 mole) and 2-(4-carbethoxyanilino)-4-chloro-6-isonicotinylhydrazino-1,3,5-triazine were taken in dioxane and the solution refluxed for 2 hr with the simultaneous dropwise addition of aqueous NaHCO₃ (10% ; 2 ml). The solution was cooled, poured on ice, filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol (95%) in 80 to 85% yields.

Antimycobacterial screening : The *in vitro* anti-tubercular activity of the hitherto synthesised 2-arylamino-4-(4-carbethoxyanilino)-6-isonicotinylhydrazino-1,3,5-triazine have been studied at 25 µg/ml concentration (solvent-acetone) against H₃₇R_v strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* using Lowenstein-Jensen medium. The procedure was duplicated with solvent for control purposes.

TABLE I—DATA OF THE 2-ARYLAMINO-4-(4-CARBETHOXYANILINO)-6-ISONICOTINYLHYDRAZINO-1,3,5-TRIAZINE

Sl. No.	Ar	m.p. °C	Activity against H ₃₇ R _v strain of <i>M. tuberculosis</i>
1.	Phenyl	150	+
2.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	218	+
3.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	231	+
4.	<i>o</i> -Carboxyphenyl	223	+
5.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	204	+
6.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	231	+
7.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	246	+
8.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	165	+
9.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	180	+
10.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	171	+
11.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	190	+
12.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	223	+

All the above compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis.

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Synthesis of Some New 1-Substituted 5-bromo-3-aryloxy acetyl hydrazono-2-indolinones as Potential Antibacterial Agents

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SEVERAL isatin analogues have been reported to possess antibacterial¹, antiviral², anthelmintic³, herbicidal⁴ and fungicidal⁵ properties. In addition to this, cysticidal⁶ and hypotensive⁷ responses have also been reported in certain isatin derivatives. Furthermore, tuberculostatic responses⁸ of aryloxy acetyl hydrazides are also well established.

Encouraged by these findings, 5-bromoisatin was condensed with *p*-substituted phenoxy acetyl hydrazides to furnish 5-bromo-3-aryloxy acetyl hydrazono-2-indolinones (I). Similarly, 5-bromo-1-methyl isatin gave 1-methyl-5-bromo-3-(*p*-substituted)-phenoxy acetyl hydrazono-2-indolinones. When compounds (I) were subjected to Mannich reaction, 1-aminomethyl-5-bromo-3-(*p*-substituted)-phenoxy acetyl hydrazono-2-indolinones were obtained and their antibacterial activity were tested.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. All the compounds were characterised by ir spectroscopy, recorded on Perkin-Elmer 137 IR spectrometer in KBr and the λ_{max} values are expressed in cm⁻¹. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel-G plates and the spots were located by I₂ vapours.

Synthesis of 5-bromoisatin (I) : The 5-bromoisatin was prepared following the literature method^{9,10}.

***N*-Methylation of isatin (II) :** This was performed by the procedure described by Harley-Manson *et al*¹¹.